

Expanding the supermassive black hole scaling relations with dynamical modelling

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Massive black holes (MBH) reside in the centers of most galaxies. While MBH are invisible, their masses (M_{BH}) can be estimated by dynamically tracing their gravitational potential (e.g., with stars or gas). Tight scaling relations between such derived M_{BH} and different properties of their host galaxies suggest that they have grown in tandem with each other [1]. To understand this co-evolution between MBH and their host galaxies, it is crucial to populate the scaling relations with precise and accurate measurements. Until now, robust M_{BH} have been determined dynamically for about 150 galaxies. However, this sample is highly heterogeneous as M_{BH} from different methods, different dynamical tracers and different instruments are compiled together (see Figure 1 in [2]). The different methods are limited and can often only be applied for certain galaxy types. Therefore, detailed cross-checks are valuable and will help to understand the intrinsic scatter in the scaling relations.

Figure 1: Black hole scaling relation over-plotted with our SMASHING galaxies (stars). Literature M_{BH} were taken from [3]. Fitting only SMASHING galaxies, the relation becomes shallower.

Stellar kinematics

About 40 per cent of robust M_{BH} have been estimated from stellar dynamics. However, even when only using stars as kinematic tracers, the results of different measurement methods can differ significantly. In the SMASHING project, we made use of high-resolution adaptive-optics assisted SINFONI and NIFS observations to derive M_{BH} for 18 early-type galaxies and one late-type galaxy [4, 5, 6, 7]. We created both dynamical Jeans and Schwarzschild models for all SMASHING galaxies

and obtained robust and homogeneously measured M_{BH} spread from the low- to the high-mass end (see Figure 1).

Our SMASHING sample greatly complements the literature sample as we not only add 19 new measurements but can also analyse a very homogeneously measured M_{BH} sample. While most of our measurements are within the scatter of the scaling relations, two low-mass galaxies show unusually over-massive black holes. The galaxies at the lower mass-end also indicate that generally more massive MBHs reside in early-type galaxies (ETG) than in late-type galaxies (LTG) for constant velocity dispersion. When fitting only the SMASHING sample, the scaling relation becomes slightly shallower but is consistent with scaling relations from the literature. This suggests that the shape of the scaling relation is not strongly influenced by the intrinsic scatter of the M_{BH} sample.

Figure 2: Black hole scaling relations for LTGs and ETGs based on stellar and (non-ALMA) gas measurements. Over-plotted are the ALMA molecular gas-based M_{BH} from the literature (dots) and our MBHBM* (stars).

Molecular gas kinematics

About one quarter of ETGs harbour compact molecular gas disks in their centers [8]. These disks often reach within the MBH sphere-of-influence and undergo acceleration by the gravitational potential. Utilizing high-resolution ALMA observations it is possible to measure this central rise in velocity. With the “Measuring BHs below the Milky-Way-mass galaxies” (MBHBM*, PI: D.D. Nguyen), we use the kinematic information of these molecular gas disks and derive robust M_{BH} for low-mass galaxies. So far, we have finished the analysis for 5 targets [9, 10, 11, 12], another 15 targets are planned to be observed. Since 2013, 20 M_{BH} have been measured with this method by different teams. In Figure 2, we com-

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pare the measurements using molecular gas kinematics with measurements from other tracers, to check if there are systematic differences between those M_{BH} samples.

The measurements from molecular gas kinematics are shown as points or stars (our measurements) and are color-coded by the morphology of the host galaxy. The shaded regions show the scaling relations derived for M_{BH} measured from other tracers for ETGs and LTGs from [13]. It is immediately visible that the main trend of the ETG scaling relations for ALMA molecular gas-based M_{BH} and other measurements are consistent. ALMA LTG on the other hand show a different picture. There have been only four measurements so far, but they seem to be significantly offset to the measurements from other kinematic tracers.

Direct cross-checks between the different tracers

Finding galaxies for which multiple methods can be applied and cross-compared is very difficult. An early-type galaxy harbouring a molecular gas disk is a prime target for such a study. We obtained adaptive-optics assisted MUSE and ALMA observations and derived the black hole mass in the early-type galaxy NGC 6958 using stars and molecular gas as kinematic tracers. Our dynamical models inferred $3.6 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$ and $4.5 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$ from stellar kinematics and molecular gas, respectively [14]. While this cross-check for NGC6958 shows a good consistency between the results of the two methods, that is not the case for other galaxies (Figure 3). Very often the gas measurement is about a factor of 2 smaller than the stellar-based measurement. The difference seems to become more significant for black holes more massive than $5 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$. The most famous example is the case of M87. For M87, stellar- and gas-based methods returned a discrepancy of a factor 2 in black hole mass [15]. New constraints could be given by the Event Horizon Telescope measurement [16] which supported the more massive stellar-based MBH for M87. Additional cross-checks are needed in the future to understand the systematic differences between the measurement methods and decrease the intrinsic scatter of the scaling relations.

Conclusion

Testing the robustness of M_{BH} estimates is crucial to better understand the scaling relations. A first consistency check reveals that within a factor of 2-3, most methods give consistent results. However, to decrease this factor, one needs to take special care of the systematics of dynamical modeling methods. We have also added 25 masses to the scaling relations ranging from the low- to the high-mass range. Our measurements are generally consistent with the scaling relations, which shows

that the in-homogeneity in M_{BH} is likely not a significant problem for the overall trend. We also find over-massive outliers from the relations which might indicate more violent merger histories for those galaxies. In the future, the analysis of the galaxy orbital distribution will provide further implications about the formation and growth of the MBHs. Furthermore, additional measurements for low-mass galaxies are needed in the future to confirm our conclusions.

Figure 3: Cross-check between stellar- and gas-based M_{BH} for ionized gas molecular gas. Our measurement is indicated as star. The dashed line is the one-to-one line where the measurements should ideally be located.

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